

India's Path of Development: A Study on FDI in Retail

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Abstract

Indian government's decision to endorse FDI in the retail sector in September 2012 which it said, is part of major economic reforms that have been stalled for months by political gridlock and came as part of a package of measures aimed at reviving growth. The current dilemma on FDI in the retail industry is a serious concern for most development thinkers. While retailing in India is a major source of its GDP, 96% of unorganized retailing and the means of subsistence of more than 40 million of Indians, on the other hand, the compulsion to invite foreign investors to invest in India to maintain steady economic growth. FDI in retail is a challenge and opportunity. The article is an attempt of examining the prospects of FDI in retail in India.

Keywords: Foreign direct investment, retail, development, License Raj, unorganized sectors

Introduction

The idea of 'development' has been associated with systematic growth, evolution, advancement, and progress. It is presented as the opposite of decay, stagnation, retardation, and underdevelopment. But the experience of varied dimensions of 'development' during the last three centuries has given rise to contentions and debate about the possibility of 'development for all'. If any model of development has certain avowed advantages, the notion of 'advantage' becomes a suspect in terms of "advantage for whom" and "who determines what 'advantage' means"? In other words, 'development' may appear to be a social construction having a discursive or cultural history. (Ghosh, 2012) The current buzz on development centers around the question of the government's decision to endorse FDI in retail and its future, which has divided the country into different poles of opinions. Each of these stands has a different perspective towards the present and future economy and society of India. Political parties are taking different stances. UPA is claiming that it would certainly boost up Indian economy and is essential to accelerate the pace of economic development of India. While on the other hand NDA together with others like Trinamul Congress and 'Left Front' are opposing vividly. It is expected to be a big day of protest with Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) already having given a call for a 'Bharat Bandh' on the same day and the CPI-ML also choosing September 20 to display its disagreement with the FDI policy. (TNN, 2012) The whole media and people are keeping their attention on the issue of FDI in India. The country is witnessing a non-violent mass movement against FDI in retail, in the form of mass rallies, slogans, and political protests. FDI in retail has become a political issue, rather than an economic one. Supporters of FDI in retail are claiming that it is high time to invite foreign market players to invest in India and set up an organized retail industry in India. It will increase the GDP rate of the country, along with the control of price inflation. Congress General Secretary Digvijay Singh has defended the Central government's stand to allow Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in retail. "The main intention of getting FDI in retail is to reduce the profit of the middlemen hence farmers would get a better price for their produce and the consumer would also reap the benefits," (ANI, 2011) Thus Government wants to establish a strong and positive correlation between FDI in retail and economic development of the country. The government has propagated the theory by the Ministry of Commerce and Industry by highlighting the employment, farmer, and consumer benefits. The political parties which are advocating FDI in retail refuse to accept that there is any dark side to it while those who are opposing the policy see none of its positive aspects. We need to examine both sides of FDI based on past experiences.

FDI in Retail in Developed Countries

FDI has proven to be beneficial, when skillfully applied, to be one of the fastest and highest means of development. The most economically developed countries like the United States are the world's largest recipients of FDI. U.S. FDI totaled \$194 billion in 2010. 84% of FDI in the U.S. in 2010 came from or through eight countries: Switzerland, the United Kingdom, Japan, France, Germany, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, and Canada. (Summary, 2011) Many other developing countries like Singapore, Indonesia, and South Korea made significant economic development in recent years. It is widely accepted that FDI inflows provide economic benefits such as increased competition, technological spillovers and innovations, and increased employment. Yet the impact of foreign investment extends far beyond economic growth. Over the past few decades, India has been remaining one of the largest recipients of FDI. Post-Independent India adhered to socialist policies. Initially, India invited FDI as a medium for acquiring advanced technology and mobilizing foreign exchange resources. India faced two severe economic crises in the form of foreign exchange and financial resource mobilization during the second five-year plan (1956 -61). Therefore, the government adopted a liberal attitude by allowing more frequent equity participation in foreign enterprises and accepting equity capital in technical collaborations. The government also provides many incentives such as tax concessions, simplification of licensing procedures, and de-reserving of some industries such as drugs, aluminum, heavy electrical equipment, fertilizers, etc. to further boost the FDI inflows in the country. "This liberal attitude of the government towards foreign capital lures investors from other advanced countries like USA, Japan, and Germany, etc. (Tandale, 2012)." In 1991, after India faced another huge balance-of-payments crisis, the collapse of the Soviet Union, which was India's major trading partner, and the Gulf War, which caused a spike in oil prices, resulted in a major balance-of-payments crisis for India. As a result, India adopted a neo-liberal policy of development to meet the challenges. India has opened its door to FDI inflows and adopted a more liberal foreign policy to restore the confidence of foreign investors. The foreign equity cap was raised to 51 percent for the existing companies. The government had allowed the use of foreign brand names for domestically produced products which was restricted earlier. New sectors such as mining, banking, telecommunications, highway construction, and management were open to foreign investors as well as to the private sector. Over the past two decades, India has moved through a process of transition in terms of increasing its GDP growth and inviting foreign investors to invest in India by stepping forward toward economic liberalization. "India being a signatory to World Trade Organization's General Agreement on Trade in Services, which include wholesale and retailing services, had to open up the retail trade sector to foreign investment." (Gupta, 2012) FDI has been proven to be beneficial so far for India in accelerating the growth of idle sectors over the past few decades.

However, the current article is dedicated to understanding the tentative role of FDI in retail in the Indian context. "Indian retail market is estimated to be US\$ 450 billion and one of the top five retail markets in the world by economic value. India is one of the fastest growing retail markets in the world, with 1.2 billion people." (Company, 2005) So far small and medium enterprises dominate the Indian retail scene. Until 2010, India's retail and logistics industry, organized and unorganized in combination, employs about 40 million Indians (3.3% of the Indian population). The typical Indian retail shops are very small. Over 14 million outlets operate in the country and only 4% of them are larger than 500 sq ft (46 m²) in size. India has about 11 shop outlets for every 1000 people. The trading sector is highly fragmented, with many intermediaries. So also, wholesale trade in India is marked by the presence of thousands of small commission agents, stockiest, and distributors who operate at a strictly local level. Apart from these, in many cases, small producers such as artisans and farmers sell their goods directly to end consumers. (ICRIER, 2007) Until 2012 organized retailing was largely absent in most rural and small towns of India. Supermarkets and similar organized retail accounted for just 4% of the total market in India. (Economist, 2008) The unorganized retail shops source their products from a chain of middlemen who mark up the product as it moves from the farmer or producer to the consumer. The vast majority of the unorganized retail shops in India employ family members, do not have the scale to procure or transport products at a high-volume wholesale level, have limited to no quality control or fake-versus-authentic product screening technology, and have no training on safe and hygienic storage, packaging or logistics. The unorganized retail shops typically offer no after-sales support or service. Finally, most transactions at unorganized retail shops are done with cash, with all sales being final.

Potential Impact in India

Today India is at the threshold of a new era, where the growth of the middle-class population is very high due to the changing scenario of economic growth in the post-liberal era. Growth of the modern urban centers together with the urban way of life demands the systematization of every aspect of life including shopping. Therefore, there is a strong urban demand for organized retailing which can assure quality, choice, and convenience in comparison to the open markets. On the contrary, most Indian shopping takes place in open markets or millions of small, independent grocery and retail shops. There is no such variety of products available for sale, consumers need to pick from a limited range of products. There is no assurance on the foodstuffs and food adulteration is common to all Indian open markets. The consumer buys from these outlets because he gets the right quality at a lower price. "Outlets such as Spinach, Big Bazaar, Reliance Retail, and Subhiksha have been delivering quality produce at lower prices." (SABNAVIS, 2008) Since 2000-2010, consumers in select Indian cities have gradually begun to experience the quality, choice, convenience, and benefits of the organized retail industry. The organized retail system enhances efficiency in the value chain. The farmer gets a better price and grows a better quality of the product; and, more importantly, is not forced to do so, and only gets into such contracts with the corporation because it benefits him. "Moreover, there is a growing trend of these shops to get associated with the larger corporate such as Hindustan Unilever, Marico, and Dabur, which have set up their own chains with such names as Super Value, Parivar and Mera respectively where the goods are sold to them at the same price as that to large retail chains on certain conditionality like focus on display or walking space for consumers." (SABNAVIS, 2008) Alternatively, the smaller vegetable and fruit vendors could become employees of the corporate retail chain, which is also taking place in a gradual manner. Further, the local shop owner, who is the last intermediary in the chain, can procure from these corporate retail stores and save on costs and sell them to the consumer. Thus, organizing retail is important from the perspective of the growing need for a fast life in urban centers.

It is also being also claimed by the proponents of FDI in retail that, farmers will profit if they can directly sell their products to the retailers; currently, in unorganized retail, they sell their products through several intermediaries, which resulted in the low income of the farmers. Another problem is the uncertainties of sales; if there are not any current demands farmers are the sole sufferers. If the farmers can set direct corporate links, they can find direct customers during the harvesting season. Multi-brand retailers like Walmart are best known for the efficient management of resources, which results in the security of the farmers to the end consumers.

Alongside, the Indian retail sector which is constituted of 96% unorganized sector does not contribute anything to the development of the nation, in the form of paying, license fees, license renewal, income tax, service tax, or other associate taxes, etc. The establishment of organized retail can help the process of development of the country where the government will also gain substantially as all the taxes and duties are paid along the way and there are no leakages together with the vast employment potential. When there are vast investments being made, can open multiple employment opportunities for different kinds of associate industries. This starts at the purchase level at the farm gate and moves across the packing, transportation, warehousing (including cold storage, when required), processing, and packaging stages before being delivered at the consumer's end. A Wall Street Journal article claims that fresh investments in Indian organized retail will generate 10 million new jobs between 2012– 2014, and about five to six million of them in logistics alone; even though the retail market is being opened to just 53 cities out of about 8000 towns and cities in India. (Reuters, 2011)

Another important sector is the logistics, or the supply chain network closely associated with retailing is very poor in India in comparison to other developing countries, strengthening the demand for FDI in retail. According to a World Bank Study conducted recently says that the Indian logistics cost is one of the highest in the world. This study shows that as far as developing countries are concerned, these costs are 6 % to 8 % of the total value of goods. In China, the cost is estimated at 10 % of the total value of goods. By comparison, the cost of logistics in India is 14 % of the total value of goods. (Vaidyanathan, 2007) Until 2010, intermediaries and middlemen in India dominated the value chain. Due to the number of intermediaries involved in the traditional Indian retail chain, norms are flouted and pricing lacks transparency. Small Indian farmers realize only 1/3rd of the total price paid by the final Indian consumer, as against 2/3rd by farmers in nations with a higher share of organized retail. (KMPG, 2010) Another interesting fact is that Indian retail has experienced limited growth, and

its spoilage of food harvest is amongst the highest in the world, because of very limited integrated cold-chain and other infrastructure. India has only 5386 standalone cold storage, having a total capacity of 23.6 million metric tons. However, 80 % of this storage is used only for potatoes. The remaining infrastructure capacity is less than 1% of the annual farm output of India and is grossly inadequate during peak harvest seasons. Farmers and producers had to go through middlemen monopolies. The logistics and infrastructure were very poor. This leads to about 30% losses in certain perishable agricultural output in India, on average, every year. Shriram Gadhve of the All-India Vegetable Growers Association (AIVGA) claims "A better cold storage would help since this could help prevent the existing loss of 34% of fruits and vegetables due to inefficient systems in place." (Kasabe, 2011)

The current FDI in retail policy can meet the challenges to a large extent; because the policy, which was cleared by the union cabinet on 24 November 2011, allows up to 51% foreign equity in a retail company, provided the total investment by foreigners in the company is at least \$100 million. Of this foreign investment, one-half is to be invested in back-end infrastructure including cold chains, refrigeration, transportation, packing, sorting, and processing. Thus, there is no doubt that India needed to make considerable investments in developing the total infrastructure of retail and logistics. There are only very few Indian companies investing in 'organize retail' in India like Reliance, Future Group, and some other small companies and they have a monopoly over the retail market; still cover only 4 percent of the total retail trade in an organized way. Organized retail is still in the stages of finding its feet in India even now. McKinsey's study claims retail productivity in India is very low compared to international peer measures. For example, the labor productivity in Indian retail was just 6% of the labor productivity in the United States in 2010. India's labor productivity in food retailing is about 5% compared to Brazil's 14%; while India's labor productivity in non-food retailing is about 8% compared to Poland's 25% (McKinsey). Though organized trade makes up over 70-80% of total trade in developed economies, India's figure is low even in comparison with other Asian developing economies like China, Thailand, South Korea, and the Philippines, all of whom have figures hovering around the 20-25% mark. These figures quite accurately reveal the relative underdevelopment of the retail industry in India. A huge market and a potent source of economy needed to be organized. On summing up Indian retail industry is still unorganized in character, as a result, a huge number of intermediaries are trading as brokers at multiple levels, as a result, original producers are not getting the right price and at the same time, the market price of the products are higher. Similarly due to the inefficient infrastructure and technology huge number of foodstuffs are spoiled in a country like India where people are suffering from malnutrition. Thus, there is a need for organize the total retail industry by allowing FDI in retail, with retaining healthy competition to manage the resources better.

Let us examine whether the above problems in retail can be solved by inviting foreign money into India. Before we get into such an endeavor, the salient features of the proposed FDI policy in multi-brand retail may be recollected. The policy, which was cleared by the union cabinet on 24 November 2011, allows up to 51% foreign equity in a retail company, provided the total investment by foreigners in the company is at least \$100 million. Of this foreign investment, one-half is to be invested in back-end infrastructure including cold chains, refrigeration, transportation, packing, sorting, and processing. These investments will be allowed only in cities with a population of more than one million. Finally, the retail company receiving the FDI is required to source at least 30% of its ware from Indian micro and small enterprises which have capital investments of not more than \$1 million. These investments will be allowed only in cities with a population of more than one million. According to the 2011 Census, there are 53 such cities out of a total of 7,935 cities and towns in the country. Finally, the retail company receiving the FDI is required to source at least 30% of its ware from Indian micro and small enterprises which have capital investments of not more than \$1 million. The demand for FDI in development becomes more prominent where the countries' major human development policies are stagnant due to the lack of economic growth. "Jagdish Bhagwati, Professor of Economics and Law at Columbia University analyzed the relationship between growth and poverty reduction, then urged the Indian parliament to extend economic reforms by freeing up the retail sector, further liberalization of trade in all sectors, and introducing labor market reforms. Such reforms Professor Bhagwati argued will accelerate economic growth and make a sustainable difference in the life of India's poorest." (Chatterjee, 2011) Thus the policy appears to be suitable for Indian soil.

While on the other hand, critics suggest that multi-brand retailing would have destabilized the Indian economic structure, since Indian manufacturing sectors are not yet ready to compete with TNCs now. It is speculated that organized retailing by foreign TNCs will not create new jobs but "displace" the existing jobs. 40 million people in India are solely dependent on unorganized retailing for their livelihood. In this scenario, FDI can have numerous negative effects, such as job loss, human rights abuses, political unrest, financial volatility,

environmental degradation, and increased cultural tensions. As Kiss analyses the situation in Hungary when the Hungarian government introduced elements of a parliamentary democracy and market economy that eventually led to the social and political exclusion of Hungarian women. Similarly, Hippert (2002), asserts that FDI and Multinational Corporations (MNCs) hamper the economic integrity and sovereignty of the developing world and states that it is women who bear the brunt of human rights abuses because of their social positions in developing countries, especially in parts of Mexico and Asia. (Michelle Herman, 2004) The introduction of FDI in retail could bring abysmal effects for the farmer due to the intensive use of technology. The biggest threat of job displacement has been realized by small-scale retailers. A strong protest against FDI in retail has been made by BJP. Accordingly, the government's decision to allow FDI was "exported concession" to the US and European countries. Allowing multi-brand retailing is a decision for which India at least today is not prepared. The entry of big players in retail seems to be beneficial and opulent for the Indian people at the first sight, but when analyzed economically, it clearly reveals that the emerging pattern comes with more important and well pronounced drawbacks. International structured retail did not create jobs but "displace" existing ones. This is because that the term 'people' includes all sections of society as a whole – producers, manufacturers, consumers, middle tradesmen. Foreign owned firms are found to have superior performance to domestically owned private firms. Furthermore, while foreign-owned firms create less demand for local producers than domestically owned firms, this is not at a level which is statistically significant. (PTI, 2012) Critics suggest that foreign retailers will source cheap, sell cheap, drive out competition, and monopolize the market. The biggest danger of allowing FDI in Indian markets was not just the threat posed to retail and services sectors, but the danger faced by the manufacturing sector. International retail sources its products internationally and domestic sources domestically. India has not taken up any reforms in the manufacturing sector. While companies from US and Europe will capture the Indian markets with cheap Chinese goods, India will become a nation of sales boys and salesgirls (PTI, 2012). The assumptions of the job displacement factor are the source of concern, inhibiting the access of FDI in retail.

On the other hand, the concept of FDI in development essentially entails the growth of idle sectors. Indian retail industry is not an idle sector it is gradually progressing several Indian companies are already doing business. The growing retail business may be affected by the foreign invasion. As AT Kearney estimated it to be Rs. 4, 00,000 crores and poised to double in 2005. On the other hand, if one used the Government's figures the retail trade in 2002-03 amounted to Rs. 3, 82,000 crores. (Guruswamy, 2005) One thing all consultants agreed upon is that the total size of the corporate owned retail business was Rs. 15,000 crores in 1999 and poised to grow to Rs.35, 000 crores by 2005 and keep growing at a rate of 40% per annum. In a recent presentation in 2007, FICCI has estimated the organized retail market in India will more than double in the next three years to touch 30 billion dollars from 14 billion dollars at present, according to a FICCI-Ernst and Young report. "The low penetration levels of organized retail in India and the fact that the market size is set to grow at a frenetic pace provide a huge potential for retailers to tap a highly unexplored market (FICCI, 2010). Over the past few decades, the growth rate of Indian retail industry is satisfactory enough without FDI. Indian retail industry is constantly evolving with its own pace, has experienced considerable growth.

Conclusion

What arises from the foregoing discussion? FDI in retail should be understood as an opportunity and challenge. In a state where the Indian retail industry is still highly unorganized but at the same time evolving towards organized retail; which resulted in the huge loss of agricultural products and capital, the government does not earn any revenues from 96% of the retail industry in India those can be used for the development of the country, the indigenous growth rate of the industry is good but not up to the international standard which reflects in the poor growth rate of the logistic industry of India. The experience of FDI in a post-reform era in India has been proven beneficial and resulted in a 6-7% annual GDP growth rate from 2002 to till date. A huge capital-driven retail industry can strengthen the total economy of India in terms of increasing the GDP rate. From this point of view, the government needs to encourage FDI as much as possible to further strengthen the economy. The current reform of FDI in retail can bring a substantial amount of advanced technology and mobilize foreign exchange resources. FDI has been proven beneficial so far for the Indian economy in terms of accelerating the pace of economic growth, together with the improvement of the construction sector, including

built-up infrastructure and construction development projects comprising housing, commercial premises, hospitals, educational institutions, recreational facilities, and city- and regional level infrastructure.

While on the other hand, the fear of jobless growth can increase the net GDP growth of the country, but at the cost of millions of people. There is no concrete estimation of the level of job displacement if India invites FDI in retail. At the current phase of development economic growth is essential to meet the developmental challenges that are facing the country. But it cannot be sufficient. What is more, it is neither feasible nor desirable to separate economic growth from distributional outcomes because they are inextricably linked with each other. This link is provided by employment creation. Jobless growth is not sustainable either in economics or in politics. The creation of employment would only reinforce economic growth through a virtuous circle of cumulative causation.

The paramount question is whether India has suitable alternatives to carry on its economic growth by denying access to foreign investments and retaining its socialist view towards one of the biggest retail markets of the world and remaining benevolent for the local retailers. Economic policies should be aimed at to the growth of indigenous industries instead of foreign firms. In a state where, 'unorganized retailing' is by far the prevalent form of trade in India constituting 96% of total trade, about four crores of India's workforce was dependent on the retail sector for a livelihood and it was "erroneous" to say that opening the market to foreign players will help both big corporate and local industry thrive. The retail outlets have their own plans to open and operate in different parts of the country and abroad. So, in turn, the producing companies find it easy to distribute and market their products through such retail chains. Their advertising and marketing work is eased and decreased. Once foreign firms monopolize the market, there will be very few small players. A market that will be controlled by a few people is contrary to the public interest. The entry of small entrepreneurs is assumed to be inhibited by the big players because they will outsource products at the cheapest rate. That will demise the possibilities of the entry of new Indian industries. To conclude the acute cost and benefit calculation is needed; there should be initial reservations towards opening multiband retails across the country, together with the regulation of the limits of import and encouraging the dependence on indigenous products to prevent Indian industries from foreign competition. Available literature has not yet proven that there is a definite correlation between FDI and jobless growth of the economy, further research is required to answer these questions.

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